

MODERN METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses about using modern methods in teaching foreign languages which made language teaching more effective and attractive. One of the goals of this article to learn many different teaching methods. A second aim is to ease uncover the opinions and thoughts that lead student’s activities as a teacher. A third goal is to present a variety of techniques some of that will be new.

Keywords: *modern methods, learning is a second language, communicative language teaching (CLT), Web based learning, suggestopedia, student’s activities.*

INTRODUCTION

Learning is a second language is a long and complex undertaking. Your whole person is affected as you struggle to reach beyond the confines of your first language and into a new language, a new culture, a new way of thinking, feeling, and acting. Total commitment, total involvement, a total physical, intellectual and emotional response are necessary to successfully send and receive messages in a second language. Many variables are involved in the acquisition process. Language learning is not a set of easy steps that can be programmed in a quick do-it-yourself kit. So

much is at stake that courses in foreign languages are often inadequate training grounds, in and of themselves, for the successful learning of a second language. Few if any people achieve fluency in a foreign language solely within the confines of the classroom.

METHODS

The main methods discussed are:

1. Communicative language teaching (CLT). Communicative language teaching (CLT) emphasize on the process of communication rather than the mastery of language. Sometime the term functional approach is use for communicative approach or communicative method. Communicative approach based on the concept of 'communicative competence' which originally introduced H D Hymns. In is article on communicative competence published in, "New origins in Linguistics" in 1971. According to geeta Nagraj, "The Development of Language Learning from based to meaning based approach". Communicative approach in was three principle 1. Which involve real communication 2. Which involves various activities. 3. Which emphasize that language is meaningful to the learners.

2. Task-Based Language Teaching. Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) is an approach that focuses on completing tasks in English. This method involves setting up real-life tasks that require students to use English to complete them. TBLT involves activities such as problem-solving, decision-making, and project work.

3. Content and Language Integrated Learning. Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) is an approach that combines language learning with subject learning. This method involves teaching a subject in English, which helps students to learn both the subject and the language at the same time. CLIL involves activities such as reading and writing about a subject in English.

4. Web based learning. Web based learning is one of the fastest developing areas. There are thousands of English web based classes that offer trainings for a variety of basic language skills such as Learning, Speaking, Reading and Writing and

are made interactive in a variety of ways. Some of the common technologies available for promotion of education are as follows: The students can correspond with native speakers of the target language using a email by creating a personal email account (g-mail, yahoo, hotmail, etc) which is free. The students can mail their home work to the teachers concerned and get it corrected in turn.

RESULTS

The article's methodologies section describes the many contemporary pedagogical frameworks and approaches that are utilized to teach English, drawing from best practices and current educational research. A through review of contemporary approaches is given, including technology integration, blended learning models, task-based language teaching (TBLT), Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), and culturally sensitive teaching techniques. This section delves into the practical application of these techniques, with a focus on enhancing language learning experiences through the utilization of technology, multimedia resources, real-world assignments, and collaborative projects

DISCUSSION

The discussion portion looks closely at the significance and ramifications of contemporary teaching approaches for improving English language instruction. It explores a number of topics, including as the changing role of technology, the significance of personalized and collaborative learning, the integration of language proficiency with subject matter content, and the emphasis on communicative competence and cultural relevance. In order to promote a reflective and interesting conversation on the changing methods used in the field of modern language instruction, this part delves deeper into the problems, possibilities, and possible future paths in this domain.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, modern methods in teaching English have revolutionized the way English we teach and learn the language. This methods give a wide range of options

for English teachers and students can learn English in more effective and practical way. Moreover, they can develop their language skills in teaching language.

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AFV ETILGAN SHAXSLARDA RESOTSIOLIZATSIYA MUAMMOLARINI TALQIN ETISHNING IJTIMOIIY-PSIXOLOGIK ASOSLARI

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***Annotatsiya:** Afv etilgan shaxslarni qayta ijtimoiylashtirishga qaratilgan jarayonlarda ularning jamiyatga tezroq qaytishi, yangi mutaxassislik, kasb-hunar egallashi, jamiyat hayoti uchun zarur bo'lgan ko'nikmalar, qonun hujjatlarida belgilangan me'yor va qoidalarga rioya qilishini ta'minlashning asoslari izohlanadi. Resotsializatsiya insonning jamiyat bilan aloqalarini tiklashi, ijobiy ijtimoiy aloqalar va u tomonidan uzilgan aloqalarni qayta o'rnatishi va ijtimoiy moslashuv jarayonlarining oson kechishi, o'zgargan turmush sharoitlariga moslashishi bilan tavsiflanadi.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** qayta ijtimoiylashtirish, ijtimoiy moslashuv, axloq tuzatish muassasalari, jinoyat motivlari, ishonchsizlik, jamiyat, reabilitatsiya.*

Ilmiy tasniflarni bayon qilish uchun "sotsiolizatsiya" va "resotsiolizatsiya" tushunchalarini farqlashimiz kerak. Fanda shaxsning "ijtimoiylashuvi" atamasi falsafiy, sotsiologik, huquqiy, psixologik, pedagogik va madaniy pozitsiyalardan kelib chiqadi. Ammo "ijtimoiylashtirish" tushunchasining barcha xilma-xil talqinlarini qisqartirish mumkin. Insonning jamiyatga kirishi, uning me'yorlari va qoidalari bilan tanishish jarayoni, insonning bevosita ijtimoiy muhitning doimiy o'zgaruvchan muhitiga moslashishi, axloqiy talablar, munosabatlar va mikromuhitning qadriyat yo'nalishlari tizimlarini idrok etish bilan tavsiflanadi. Axloq tuzatish muassasalaridan ozod qilingan shaxslar jazoni o'tashdan keyin ham,

muddatidan oldin ham ijtimoiy moslashuvga muhtoj. Ular yana jinoyatchi bo'lib qolmasligi uchun jamiyat manfaatlarini ko'zlab yordam berish kerak.

So'zning tor ma'nosida resotsializatsiya - bu shaxs tomonidan ilgari o'zlashtirilganidan tubdan farq qiladigan qadriyatlar va me'yorlarni o'zlashtirishi tushuniladi. Bu tushunchada ma'lum odamlar guruhlariga tegishli bo'ladi. Shu ma'noda resotsializatsiya deganda, u bir dunyodan ikkinchisiga "o'tganda" shaxsning o'zgarishi (ozodlikka qaytishi, emigratsiya, yangi dinni egallash, yuqoriga vertikal harakatchanlik, uzoq muddatli kasalxonaga yotqizish) tushuniladi.

Agar insonga, uning qadr-qimmatiga minimal hurmatni ta'minlash va malakali psixologik yordam ko'rsatishning iloji bo'lmasa, jinoiy jazoning ijobiy ta'siri nolga kamayadi.

A. Levitskiyning fikricha, resotsializatsiyaga quyidagi omillar ta'sir qiladi va shu bilan birga moslashish jarayonini osonlashtiradi:

-shaxs rivojlanayotgan madaniyatning ijtimoiylashuv darajasi;

-aqliy moslashuvni shakllantirish, ya'ni, ma'lum bir madaniyatda shaxsiy ehtiyojlarni qondirish;

-atrof-muhitning qasddan va qasddan bo'lmagan ta'sirini qayta ijtimoiylashtirishga moslashtirish. Qayta ijtimoiylashtirish - bu penitensiar va penitensiardan keyingi bosqichlardan iborat murakkab ko'p qirrali jarayon bo'lib, ularning har birida jinoyat sodir etgan shaxslarga har tomonlama ta'sir ko'rsatish kerak. Qayta ijtimoiylashtirishning asosiy prinsipi jinoyatchining rivojlanishi uchun ma'lum potensial imkoniyatlarga ega ekanligini va albatta qonunga bo'ysunuvchi fuqaroning hayotini davom ettirish qobiliyatini shakllantirishi kerak. Ozodlikka chiqarilgandan keyin jamiyatda muvaffaqiyatli moslashish uchun zarur shart-sharoitlarni yaratish bo'yicha tadbirlar amalga oshirilishi kerak. Afv etilgan shaxslarni qayta ijtimoiylashtirishning ikki tomoni bor:

-ozodlikka chiqarilgan shaxslarni psixologiyasining tegishli o'zgarishi;

-jamiyatning uni qabul qilishga roziligi.

Ikkinchisi bilan moddiy va maishiy xarakterdagi qiyinchiliklar paydo bo'lishi mumkin. qayta ijtimoiylashtirish maqsadiga erishilganda yangi jinoyatlar sodir etilishining oldini olish maqsadi ham amalga oshadi. Ijtimoiylashgan shaxs mahkumlar jamoasida emas, balki jamiyatda muvaffaqiyatga erishishga undaydi.

Qonun chiqaruvchining jinoiy jazoning maqsad va vazifalariga nisbatan bunday noaniq qarashi davlatning o'z fuqarolariga bo'lgan e'tiboridan va aybdorni aybdor deb topish va unga nisbatan u yoki bu jazo chorasini qo'llash, maqsadli vositalardan foydalanish orqali ijobiy natijaga erishish istagidan dalolatdir. Kuni kecha 8-dekabr O'zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasining 31-yilligi munosabati bilan 334 nafar shaxs afv etildi. Prezident farmoniga muvofiq, sodir etgan jinoyati uchun jazoni ijro etish muassasalari va probatsiya organlarida jazo o'tayotgan hamda qilmishiga chin ko'ngildan pushaymon bo'lgan va tuzalish yo'liga qat'iy o'tgan 334 nafar shaxs afv etildi. Shundan:

-34 nafari asosiy jazodan to'liq ozod etilgan;

-249 nafari jazoni o'tashdan muddatidan ilgari shartli ozod qilingan;

-6 nafarining ozodlikdan mahrum etish jazosi yengilroq jazo bilan almashtirilgan;

-45 nafar shaxsga tayinlangan ozodlikdan mahrum etish jazosining muddatlari qisqartirilgan. Afv etilganlarning 18 nafari chet el fuqarolari, 23 nafari ayol, 15 nafari 60 yoshdan oshgan shaxslar hamda 88 nafari taqiqlangan tashkilotlar faoliyatida qatnashgan shaxslar tashkil etadi.²⁵ Qayta ijtimoiylashtirish maqsadiga erishilganda yangi jinoyatlar sodir etilishining oldini olish maqsadi ham amalga oshadi. Ijtimoiylashgan shaxs mahkumlar jamoasida emas, balki jamiyatda muvaffaqiyatga erishishga intiladi. Mahkumlarni, ozodlikka chiqarilgan shaxslarni qayta ijtimoiylashtirish davlat siyosatining yo'nalishlaridan biri hisoblanadi.

Ozodlikdan mahrum qilish jazosini o'tagan shaxslarni jamoat munosabatlari va

fuqarolik jamiyatiga qo'shish orqali jinoyatlar takrorlanishining oldini olish va qonunga itoatkorlik xulq-atvorini shakllantirish bo'yicha chora-tadbirlar majmuini

²⁵ <https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/6916/>.

o'z ichiga oladi. Shu maqsadda jazoni ijro etish tizimi muassasalari xodimlari mahkumlar bilan jazoni o'tash davrida ham, ular ozodlikdan mahrum qilish joylaridan ozod etilgunga qadar ham erkinlik, ularni tayyorlash uchun ijtimoiy, huquqiy, iqtisodiy, psixologik, pedagogik va tibbiy xarakterdagi kompleks choratadbirlar amalga oshirilishi kerak.

Ozodlikka chiqarilgan shaxslarda insonga, jamiyatga, mehnatga, insoniyat jamiyatining normalari va an'analariga ijobiy munosabatni shakllantirish va qonunga bo'ysunish jarayonlarini tashkil etish resotsiolizatsiyani ta'minlanishi bilan bog'liq bo'ladi. Qayta ijtimoiylashtirish mahkumlarning, afv etilgan shaxslarning shaxsini o'zgartirish jarayoni sifatida qaraladi, bu uning rivojlanishining obyektiv va subyektiv sharoitlari ta'siri ostida sodir bo'ladi. Jinoiy jazoni ijro etuvchi muassasalar va organlarning xodimlari, boshqa davlat va jamoat tuzilmalari vakillari, jinoiy jazoni o'tayotgan shaxslarning qarindoshlari va yaqinlari, shuningdek, boshqa mahkumlarga tashqi ta'sir ko'rsatadilar.

Mahkumlarni tuzatish bir vaqtning o'zida jazoni ijro etish va axloq tuzatish choralarini qo'llash natijasida ko'rib chiqiladi. "Oraliq xulosa sifatida shuni aytishimiz mumkinki, qayta ijtimoiylashtirish maqsadiga erishilganda yangi jinoyatlar sodir etilishining oldini olish maqsadi ham amalga oshadi. Ijtimoiylashtirish shaxs mahkumlar jamoasida emas, balki jamiyatda muvaffaqiyatga erishishga undaydi. Qonunni buzgan shaxsni tuzatishning butun jarayoni - tergov va sudlanganlikdan tortib, axloq tuzatish muassasasida qolishgacha va undan chiqqanidan keyin ma'lum muddat - qayta ijtimoiylashtirish jarayoni doirasida amalga oshiriladi."²⁶

²⁶ М. Д. Шаргородский СИСТЕМА НАКАЗАНИЙ И ИХ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ. 1968 №11. С-57

Xulosa qilib shuni aytishimiz mumkinki,ozodlikdan mahrum qilish jazosini o'tash davrida,ozodlikka chiqarilgandan so'ng amalga oshiriladigan ijtimoiy faoliyatga qarindoshlar, do'stlar, qo'shnilar va hamkasblar bilan aloqalarni tiklash va rivojlantirishga qaratilgan faoliyatlarga ham alohida ahamiyat berish kerak.

Oila mahkumga nisbatan axloq tuzatish muassasasida bo'lgan vaqtida ham, ozod qilinganidan keyin ham ijtimoiylashtirish funksiyasini bajaradigan asosiy ijtimoiy institutdir. Tug'ilishdan to o'lingacha shaxs ijtimoiylashuv jarayonlariga kiradi. Moslashuv shaxsning ijtimoiylashuvining asosiy bosqichidir. Shunga ko'ra, sotsiolizatsiya moslashishni o'z ichiga olgan universal jarayondir. Ozodlikdan mahrum qilish jazosiga hukm qilingan shaxslar o'rtasida ijtimoiylashuv jarayonlarini qayta tiklash vazifasi paydo bo'ladi.

Jazoni o'tashdan ozod qilingan shaxslarni ishga joylashtirish bo'yicha ijroiya qo'mitalari ko'rsatmalari korxonalar, muassasa va tashkilotlar bilan hamkorlikda ishlash va ozod qilingan shaxslar bandligini ta'minlash resotsiolizatsiya jarayonini muvaffaqiyatli amalga oshirish uchun xizmat qiladi.

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